

Studies on Thio Salts. Part V. Formation of Thio Salt from Tellurous Sulphide

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Stability constants of the anions TeS_3^{2-} and $\text{TeS}_2\text{O}^{2-}$ have been evaluated from solubility studies. Taking the effective mass of slightly soluble tellurous sulphide constant, the values for the stability constants of the anions have been found to be 4.1×10^7 and 1.8×10^4 , respectively. The conductometric and potentiometric studies reveal that thio-oxytellurite behaves as a dibasic acid and the values for its first and second dissociation constants are 2.0×10^{-9} and 3.2×10^{-11} respectively.

In the earlier communication¹ the formation of thio- and thio-oxy complexes of tellurium(IV) during our study on the precipitation of its sulphide in alkaline medium was reported. We have now studied the dissolution of tellurous sulphide in alkaline medium to ascertain the stability constant of these complexes, using solubility measurements. Conductometric and potentiometric methods have also been applied to assess the acidic nature and strength of thio-oxytellurite.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tellurous sulphide suspension was prepared by treating tellurous thio-salt solution with HCl and washing the fresh precipitate of tellurous sulphide till the wash water became free of Cl^- ions. Volume of the suspension was made to a litre and kept in an air-tight Jena glass bottle. An aliquot of the suspension (5 ml), drawn after shaking the container well, yielded very nearly the same amount of a solid residue every time.

Sodium hydrosulphide and hydrogen sulphide solutions were prepared as described earlier¹ and solutions of NaOH and KCl were prepared, using A. R. grade chemicals. The method for preparation of reaction mixtures and estimation of tellurium as TeS_2 was the same as described earlier¹.

Dissolution of Tellurous Sulphide in H_2S Solution in presence of Varying Amounts of NaOH

To reaction mixtures containing constant quantities of tellurous sulphide, H_2S , and KCl in solution varying amounts of NaOH were added. The observations on the dissolution of tellurous sulphide and measurement of pH are recorded in Table I. Assuming that all the sulphide in dissolved state is present as TeS_3^{2-} , the last column represents the values for the concentration ratio $[\text{TeS}_3^{2-}]/[\text{S}^{2-}]$. The concentration of sulphide ions has

1. Dubey, *Vijnana Parishad Anus.*, 1962, 3, Part V, 117.

been calculated from the amount of HS^- ions remaining free after the formation of the thio anion TeS_3^{2-} . In the calculations the known values for the dissociation constants of H_2S and measured values of pH were used. The effect of ionic strength was neglected. The dissociation of H_2S remaining in solution had not been taken in account as its effect on the total sulphide concentration, which was obtained from the dissociation of HS^- , was considered to be negligible.

TABLE I

0.03515M- H_2S soln.=30 ml. 0.50M-KCl soln.=10 ml. 0.1140M- TeS_2 suspension
=5 ml. NaOH soln.=0.4651M. Total volume=50.0 ml.

NaOH added.	*NaHF formed.	* TeS_2 dissolved.	* HS^- remaining free.	pH.	$[\text{TeS}_3^{2-}]/[\text{S}^{2-}]$.
0.00 ml	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.7	..
0.50	4.85	0.44	3.77	6.5	3.0×10^7
1.00	9.30	1.52	6.25	6.7	4.0
1.50	13.95	3.50	6.94	7.1	4.0
2.00	18.60	5.57	7.46	7.1	5.0
					Av. 3.8×10^7

*Expressed in g. mol./litre $\times 10^{-3}$.

The values obtained for the ratio $[\text{TeS}_3^{2-}]/[\text{S}^{2-}]$ provide the equilibrium constant of the following reaction:

The sulphide ions are obtained due to:

Hydrogen ions thus liberated react further with an equivalent amount of HS^- to produce molecular hydrogen sulphide. Therefore in the calculations, the concentration of free HS^- ions has been obtained by deducting 2g. moles of HS^- for every mole of TeS_2 dissolved from the total amount of HS^- present in the system.

Dissolution of Tellurous Sulphide in Sodium Hydrosulphide Solution

Reaction mixtures containing constant amounts of tellurous sulphide suspension and potassium chloride solution were treated with varying amounts of sodium hydrosulphide solution. The observations on the dissolution of tellurous sulphide and measurement of pH are recorded in Table II. Assuming that all the tellurous sulphide in dissolved state is present as thio anion, TeS_3^{2-} , the concentration ratio $[\text{TeS}_3^{2-}]/[\text{S}^{2-}]$ is shown in the last column. The concentration of sulphide ions was calculated as mentioned earlier¹.

Considering the accuracy of pH measurements limited to only one place after decimal, the value obtained for the equilibrium constant here is in fair agreement to the one shown in Table I.

The representative value of the equilibrium constant can be taken as average of the values recorded in Tables I and II, i.e., 4.1×10^7 . This value is only apparent stability constant as it includes an unknown constant factor, i.e., solubility of tellurous sulphide.

TABLE II

0.50M-KCl soln.=10 ml. 0.1140M-TeS₂ suspension=5 ml. NaHS soln.=0.0537M.
Total volume = 50.0ml.

NaHS added.	*HS ⁻ added.	*TeS ₂ dissolved.	pH.	[TeS ₃ ²⁻]/[S ²⁻].
10.0 ml	1.074×10 ⁻²	3.212×10 ⁻³	7.3	3.1×10 ⁷
15.0	1.811	5.172	7.3	4.5
20.0	2.148	7.310	7.3	4.5
25.0	2.895	9.156	7.3	4.5
30.0	3.222	11.380	7.3	4.0

Av. 4.3×10⁷

*Expressed in g. mol./litre.

Dissolution Study of Tellurous Sulphide in NaOH Solution

Reaction mixtures containing constant amounts of tellurous sulphide suspension and potassium chloride solution were treated with varying amounts of NaOH solution. The observations are noted in Table III. Assuming that all the tellurium sulphide in dissolved state is TeS₂O²⁻, the last column represents the concentration ratio [TeS₂O²⁻]/[OH⁻]², the concentration of OH⁻ ions being obtained from the measured pH values.

TABLE III

0.5 M-KCl soln.=10 ml. 0.1140 M-TeS₂susp.=5 ml. NaOH=0.0465M.
Total volume = 50.0ml.

NaOH added.	*NaOH.	*TeS ₂ dissolved.	pH.	[TeS ₂ O ²⁻]/[OH ⁻] ² .
10.0 ml	0.930×10 ⁻²	2.65×10 ⁻³	10.6	1.7×10 ⁴
15.0	1.395	4.74	10.7	1.9
20.0	1.860	6.78	10.8	1.7
25.0	2.326	8.07	10.8	2.2
30.0	2.791	10.84	10.9	1.7

Av. 1.8×10⁴

Expressed in g.mol./litre.

The values obtained for the concentration ratio [TeS₂O²⁻]/[OH⁻]² are fairly constant. The average value for the ratio is 1.8×10⁴. This value denoted by *K'* is the equilibrium constant of the reaction:

the effective mass of slightly soluble tellurous sulphide being constant. In other words, it is the apparent stability constant of the thio-oxy anion. The study of stability constants for the anions TeS₃²⁻ and TeS₂O²⁻ reveals that the former is more stable and this explains greater solubility of TeS₂ in sodium hydrosulphide solution than in sodium hydroxide solution, though the solutions of the former are less alkaline.

Conductometric and Potentiometric Studies

A thio-oxytellurite solution (0.0744M-NaOH+0.01908M-TeS₂) was prepared by treating tellurium sulphide suspension with an excess of NaOH solution of known strength

and making the volume to 250.0 ml. Ten-ml portions of this solution were treated with varying amounts of HCl (0.0351M), total volume being made to 50.0. ml in each case.

FIG. 1

The reaction mixtures thus prepared were shaken well and kept at a constant temperature (30°) for 18 hours. The electrical conductance and pH of these solutions measured are represented in Fig. 1 where observed conductance and pH are plotted against the equivalents of alkali (with respect to TeS_2) remaining unneutralised by acid.

Fig. 1 shows that there is a rapid fall in the observed conductance in earlier stages due to neutralisation of excess alkali present. This proceeds to the point where two equivalents of OH^- remain unneutralised for

one equivalent of tellurous sulphide. Beyond this, the anion $\text{TeS}_2\text{O}^{2-}$ reacts with acid as:

The above reaction is completed at the point where the stoichiometric ratio of TeS_2 to alkali remaining unneutralised approaches 1:1. Further addition of acid leads to the reactions suggested below:

This continues till nearly all the alkali present in the system is neutralised by HCl after which the conductance rises rapidly. The two flat portions of the curve in the equivalent ranges of 2.1 and 1.0 suggest the titration of salt of weak dibasic acid ($\text{H}_2\text{TeS}_2\text{O}$) and strong alkali (NaOH) in steps. The behaviour of thio-oxy tellurite as dibasic acid appears to be quite parallel to that of thio-oxytellurate²³.

The values of pH at 1.5 and 0.5 equivalent points in Fig. 1 at half neutralisation points of the acids HTeS_2O^- and $\text{H}_2\text{TeS}_2\text{O}$ are 10.5 and 8.7 respectively. The H^+ -ion concentrations corresponding to these pH values are 3.2×10^{-11} and 2.0×10^{-9} respectively and these may be taken as the second and first dissociation constants of the acid $\text{H}_2\text{TeS}_2\text{O}$.

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